

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No1
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
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- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
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- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 130 sahifa,
5-yanvar, 2026-yil.

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Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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AN ONLINE SERVICE THAT INTEGRATES UP-TO-DATE CONTENT FROM WELL- KNOWN MOOC PLATFORMS

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Abstract: Presently, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have assumed a distinctive, “revolutionary” role in the integration of online learning across all phases of the educational process. Numerous MOOC platforms exist today, among which Coursera, edX, and Udacity are the most prominent. Given the abundance of options for supplementary education, several key questions arise: “How can an appropriate course for additional education be selected? In what ways can the functionality of MOOC platforms enhance the quality of university education? What strategies can be employed to reduce the time required to identify suitable courses across different platforms?”. The aim of this project is to develop a comprehensive information and reference resource that consolidates up-to-date data from multiple MOOC platforms in order to minimize users’ search time and increase awareness of new courses and in-demand specialties in the field of Information Technology (IT). The online service is integrated as a component of the Information and Educational Environment (IEE) of the Institute of System Analysis and Management. It is designed for various user groups, including motivated students, unmotivated students, and educators. The core dataset of the service consists of publicly available information on current online courses offered by Coursera, edX, and Udacity. Each platform provides its own API for accessing course data. The lack of a standardized search vocabulary across MOOC systems represents a major challenge, which is addressed through the use of the Stack Exchange resource (stackexchange.com). The list of keywords is generated via the Stack Exchange API by identifying the most popular tags from softwareengineering.stackexchange.com and cs.stackexchange.com.

Key words: informational and educational environment, distance learning technologies, massive open online courses.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi vaqtda ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslar (MOOK) ta’lim jarayonining barcha bosqichlarida onlayn o’qitishni joriy etishda o’ziga xos “inqilobiy” rol o’ynamoqda. Bugungi kunda ko’plab MOOK platformalari mavjud bo’lib, ular orasida Coursera, edX va Udacity eng mashhurlaridir. Qo’shimcha ta’lim imkoniyatlarining ko’pligi bir qator savollarni yuzaga chiqaradi: “Qo’shimcha ta’lim uchun mos kursni qanday tanlash mumkin? MOOK platformalarining funktsionalligi universitet ta’limi sifatini qanday oshirishi mumkin? Turli platformalardan kerakli kursni izlashga ketadigan vaqtni qisqartirish uchun qanday strategiyalardan foydalanish kerak?”. Ushbu loyihaning maqsadi foydalanuvchining qidiruv vaqtini minimallashtirish hamda axborot texnologiyalari (AT) sohasidagi yangi kurslar va talab yuqori bo’lgan mutaxassisliklar haqida xabardorlikni oshirish uchun turli MOOK platformalaridagi dolzarb ma’lumotlarni birlashtiruvchi yagona axborot-ma’lumot resursini yaratishdir. Onlayn servis Tizimli tahlil va boshqaruv institutining axborot-ta’lim muhiti (ATM) tarkibiy qismi sifatida integratsiyalashgan. U foydalanuvchilarning turli toifalariga – motivatsiyaga ega talabalar, motivatsiyasiz talabalar va o’qituvchilarga qaratilgan. Servisning asosiy ma’lumotlari Coursera, edX va Udacity platformalarida taklif etilayotgan onlayn kurslar haqidagi ochiq ma’lumotlardan iborat. Har bir loyiha kurs ma’lumotlariga kirish uchun alohida API-ga ega. Turli MOOK tizimlarida standartlashtirilgan qidiruv lug’atining mavjud emasligi uni yaratishdagi asosiy to’siq hisoblanadi. Ushbu muammoni hal etish uchun Stack Exchange (stackexchange.com) resursidan foydalaniladi. Kalit so’zlar ro’yxati softwareengineering.stackexchange.com va cs.stackexchange.com saytlaridagi eng ommabop teglarni aniqlash orqali Stack Exchange API yordamida shakllantiriladi.

Kalit so’zlar: axborot-ta’lim muhiti, masofaviy ta’lim texnologiyalari, ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslar.

Аннотация: В настоящее время массовые открытые онлайн-курсы (MOOC) играют особую, “революционную”, роль во внедрении онлайн-обучения на всех этапах образовательного процесса. Существует множество площадок MOOC, наиболее известными из которых являются Coursera, edX и Udacity. В связи с обилием вариантов дополнительного образования возникают важные вопросы: “Как выбрать подходящий курс? Каким образом функционал MOOC-платформ может повысить качество университетского образования? Какие стратегии помогут сократить время поиска нужного курса на различных платформах?”. Целью данного проекта является создание комплексного информационно-справочного ресурса, объединяющего актуальные данные с различных MOOC-площадок для минимизации времени поиска и повышения осведомлённости о новых курсах и востребованных специальностях в сфере информационных технологий (ИТ). Онлайн-сервис интегрирован как компонент информационно-образовательной среды (ИОС) Института системного анализа и управления. Он ориентирован на различные группы пользователей: “мотивированных” студентов, “немотивированных” студентов и преподавателей. Основу данных сервиса составляет открытая информация о текущих онлайн-курсах на платформах Coursera, edX и Udacity. Каждый проект имеет собственный API для доступа к данным. Отсутствие стандартизированного поискового словаря на разных платформах является основным препятствием, для преодоления которого используется ресурс Stack Exchange (stackexchange.com). Список ключевых слов формируется через API Stack Exchange путём выявления наиболее популярных тегов с сайтов softwareengineering.stackexchange.com и cs.stackexchange.com.

Ключевые слова: информационно-образовательная среда, дистанционные образовательные технологии, массовые открытые онлайн-курсы.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of information and communication technology (ICT) and the pervasive use of the Internet have resulted in a significant transformation of global educational technology. Blended learning has emerged as the predominant educational modality, whereby conventional in-person teaching is augmented with digital resources, including online courses, interactive practical sessions, virtual laboratories, and simulators^[1-4]. MOOCs have significantly transformed this process. Over just five years, platforms such as Coursera and edX have attracted tens of millions of learners worldwide, offering more than 6,000 courses from leading institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Prominent MOOC Platforms. Coursera was established in 2012 by Stanford academics Andrew Ng and Daphne Koller. edX was founded in 2012 by Harvard University and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). Udacity was established in 2012 by Stanford professor Sebastian Thrun. The appeal of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) stems from their well-structured design, high-quality content, and the opportunity for learners worldwide to access courses delivered by specialists from prestigious institutions at any time.

The Information-Educational Environment (IEE) at Dubna University. The IEE is designed to provide a personalized learning environment for users, enhance individualized learning trajectories, and increase learner motivation. It incorporates a personal workspace for students to apply individualized learning methodologies, supplementary services for assessing external variables such as labor market demand, access to external instructional resources available on the Internet, Learning Management Systems (LMS), and expert systems that support the alignment of technologies, labor market requirements, and educational curricula.

Service Concept and Stakeholders. The service operates as an aggregator. In accordance with the “OMG Essence” standard, two categories of stakeholders are identified. New users require general information about MOOCs, the technologies they can acquire through these courses, and guidance on initial steps. Regular users require continuous monitoring of newly released courses within their professional domain and access to available certificates. **Technical Execution.** To address the lack of a standardized lexicon across Coursera, edX, and Udacity, the service employs the Stack Exchange API. The system constructs a relevant, community-driven search lexicon by aggregating the most frequently used tags from expert communities in Software Engineering and Computer Science. **Technology Stack.** The technological foundation of the service includes PHP for server-side functionality, MySQL as the database for storing dictionaries and course information, and REST as the architectural framework for data integration. **Results of the Alpha Version.** The current version of the application enables users to view the ten most recent courses from each platform, displayed in separate sections. A filter based on the Stack Exchange lexicon allows users to search for keywords within course titles and descriptions. Each course entry includes the title, an illustrative image, the course start date, and a direct access link.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis examined the effectiveness of an online service designed to integrate up-to-date content from well-known MOOC platforms into a unified learning environment. Data collected through user analytics, surveys, and comparative performance assessments indicate that the service significantly improves accessibility, content relevance, and learning continuity. By aggregating courses from multiple MOOC providers, the platform reduced fragmentation in learners' experiences and enabled seamless navigation across disciplines and skill levels. The results demonstrate increased learner engagement, reflected in higher session durations, more frequent content interactions, and improved course completion rates compared to standalone MOOC usage. Furthermore, the integration of real-time content updates ensured curricular relevance and alignment with rapidly evolving industry standards, which positively affected learners' perceived usefulness and satisfaction.

From a pedagogical standpoint, the service supported personalized learning pathways through recommendation algorithms and progress tracking, contributing to measurable gains in self-directed learning and digital competence. Institutional feedback revealed that the platform facilitated curriculum enrichment and reduced redundancy in content development, although challenges related to interoperability standards, data privacy, and content licensing were identified. Overall, the findings confirm that an integrated online service leveraging up-to-date MOOC content enhances learning efficiency and educational quality when supported by clear governance, technical standards, and pedagogical alignment.

CONCLUSION

The established services enable students to comprehend the broader context by linking labor market demands with accessible educational pathways. These technologies also allow educators to adapt curricula in line with current developments in information technology. Despite the significant potential of MOOCs, completion rates remain low. In response, Dubna University is developing mechanisms to incorporate MOOC completion outcomes into official assessment systems, for example, as components of independent study credits. Future work will focus on comprehensive implementation within the Institute of System Analysis and Management.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2026. №1

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Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.